

Galaxies in our universe seem to be achieving an impossible feat. They are rotating with such speed that the gravity generated by their observable matter could not possibly hold them together; they should have torn themselves apart long ago. The same is true of galaxies in clusters, which leads scientists to believe that something we cannot see is at work. They think something we have yet to detect directly is giving these galaxies extra mass, generating the extra gravity they need to stay intact. This strange and unknown matter was called "dark matter" since it is not visible.

Dark matter

Unlike normal matter, dark matter does not interact with the electromagnetic force. This means it does not absorb, reflect or emit light, making it extremely hard to spot. In fact, researchers have been able to infer the existence of dark matter only from the gravitational effect it seems to have on visible matter. Dark matter seems to outweigh visible matter roughly six to one, making up about 27% of the universe. Here's a sobering fact: The matter we know and that makes up all stars and galaxies only accounts for 5% of the content of the universe! But what is dark matter? One idea is that it could contain "super symmetric particles" – hypothesized particles that are partners to those already known in the [Standard Model](#). Experiments at the [Large Hadron Collider](#) (LHC) may provide more direct clues about dark matter.

Many theories say the dark matter particles would be light enough to be produced at the LHC. If they were created at the LHC, they would escape through the detectors unnoticed. However, they would carry away energy and momentum, so physicists could infer their existence from the amount of energy and momentum “missing” after a collision. Dark matter candidates arise frequently in theories that suggest physics beyond the Standard Model, such as super symmetry and extra dimensions. One theory suggests the existence of a “Hidden Valley”, a parallel world made of dark matter having very little in common with matter we know. If one of these theories proved to be true, it could help scientists gain a better understanding of the composition of our universe and, in particular, how galaxies hold together.

Dark energy

Dark energy makes up approximately 68% of the universe and appears to be associated with the vacuum in space. It is distributed evenly throughout the universe, not only in space but also in time – in other words, its effect is not diluted as the universe expands. The even distribution means that dark energy does not have any local gravitational effects, but rather a global effect on the universe as a whole. This leads to a repulsive force, which tends to accelerate the expansion of the universe. The rate of expansion and its acceleration can be measured by observations based on the Hubble law. These measurements, together with other scientific data, have confirmed the existence of dark energy and provide an estimate of just how much of this mysterious substance exists.

D^0 invariant mass

Background signals

Mass of the origin = 1815 MeV/c²

Mass of the closure = 1915 MeV/c²

∴ Range of the signals

= 1815 MeV/c² to 1915 MeV/c²

Mean value of the range

$$= \frac{1915 - 1815}{2} = 50 \text{ MeV/c}^2$$

clusters are formed at two regions. The central mean region is very less populated by the particles.

First number of background
particles $\rightarrow$ 1815 MeV/c² to
1840 MeV/c²

Quantity of D⁰ candidates
= 150

1815 MeV/c² $\rightarrow$ 150 D⁰ candidates
1820 MeV/c² $\rightarrow$ 150 D⁰ candidates
1915 MeV/c² $\rightarrow$ 100 + 150 - 100

2

$$= 100 + 25$$

= 125 D⁰ candidate

As the mass of b^0 candidates increases, the quantity of D^0 candidates increases

Mass $\uparrow$ $\longrightarrow$ Quantity $\downarrow$

$\therefore$ Mass $\propto \frac{1}{\text{Quantity}}$

i.e. Mass $\neq$ Quantity

= constant

Thus, the total energy
is conserved

Signals :-

Range $\rightarrow$ 1840 MeV/c² to
1890 MeV/c²

Mean invariant mass

$$= \frac{1890 - 1840}{2}$$

$$= 25 \text{ MeV/c}^2$$

Quantity of D^0 candidates
at $1240 \text{ MeV}/c^2 = 150$

Quantity of D^0 candidates
at the mean = 800

Quantity of D^0 candidates
at $1890 \text{ MeV}/c^2 \approx 150$

The quantity increases from
the starting value till the mean
Then it starts reducing as it
reaches the end of the main
range, till it reaches the
point of interaction with the

background signal.

① From start to mean

Man $\uparrow$ $\longrightarrow$ Quantity $\uparrow$

Man $\propto$ Quantity

$$\frac{\text{Man}}{\text{Quantity}} = \text{constant}$$

② From mean to end

Man $\uparrow$ $\longrightarrow$ Quantity $\downarrow$

Mean α 1
Quantity

Mean $\neq$ Quantity
 $\approx$ constant

Thus,
Start to end

$$= \textcircled{1} + \textcircled{2} \text{ [By combination]}$$

$$= \frac{M \text{ am}}{\text{Quantity}} + (M \text{ am} \times \text{Quantity})$$

$$= \text{constant}$$

$$\therefore \frac{M}{Q} + (M \times Q) = K$$

$$\Im \left[\frac{1 + \phi}{\phi} \right] \approx k$$

$$\Im \left[\frac{\phi^2 + 1}{\phi} \right] \approx k$$

$$m[q^2 + 1] = qk$$

$$m[q^2 + 1] - kq = 0$$

$$\frac{d}{dq} \{ m[q^2 + 1] \} - k \cdot \frac{d}{dq} [q] = 0$$

$$m \left\{ \frac{d}{dq} [q^2 + 1] \right\} - k(1) = 0$$

$$m \left\{ \frac{d}{dq} [q^2] + \frac{d}{dq} [1] \right\} - k = 0$$

$$m \left\{ 2Q + 0 \right\} - k = 0$$

$$2mQ - k = 0$$

$$\therefore mQ = \frac{k}{2} \quad \therefore mQ = \frac{1}{2}$$

where $k = 1$

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$$\frac{m}{Q} + mQ = k$$

$$\frac{m}{Q} + \frac{1}{2} = k$$

$$\frac{2m + Q}{2Q} = k$$

$$2m + Q = 2Qk$$

$$2m = 2kQ - Q = Q(2k - 1)$$

$$2M = Q(2k-1)$$

$$\therefore Q = \frac{2M}{(2k-1)}$$

Decay time :-

Background :-

In 0.1 seconds, 10^{-1} fraction of D^0
candidates decay

In 10 ps, 10^{-4} fraction of D^0
candidates decay

Mean decay time

$$= \frac{10 - 0}{2} = 5 \text{ ps}$$

$\ln$ 5 ps, $10^{-3.5}$ D^0 candidates
decay

Decay time $\uparrow$ $\longrightarrow$ Quantity $\downarrow$

$$\text{Decay time} \propto \frac{1}{\text{Quantity}}$$

$$\therefore \text{Decay time} \times \text{Quantity} = \text{constant}$$

Signal 1 -

At 0 p.s. , $10^{-1.75}$ D^0 candidates
decay
-3.5 σ

At $5 \text{ ps}, 10^{-3.5} D^0$ candidates
decay

At $10 \text{ ps}, 10^{-4} D^0$ candidates
decay

Decay time $\uparrow$ $\longrightarrow$ quantity $\downarrow$

$$\therefore \text{Decay time} \propto \frac{1}{\text{Quantity}}$$

Decay time $\times$ quantity
= constant

Total signal decay value
= Background + signal

$$\begin{aligned} &= (\text{Decay time})_D * (\text{Quantity})_D \\ &+ (\text{Decay time})_S * (\text{Quantity})_S \\ &\equiv 2 \left[\text{Time} * \text{Quantity} \right] \\ &\quad \quad \quad \rightarrow \text{constant} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathcal{L}(TQ) = k$$

$$Q = \frac{k}{2T} \rightarrow \textcircled{I}$$

From $\textcircled{I}$ and $\textcircled{II}$

$$Q = \frac{2M}{2k-1} = \frac{k}{2T}$$

$$2M[2T] = k[2k-1]$$

$$4MT = 2k^2 - k$$

$$4mT = 2k^2 - k$$

$$\frac{4mT}{2k^2 - k} = 1$$

$$\frac{4MT}{2k^2 - k} - 1 = 0$$

$$\therefore Q = \frac{4MT}{2k^2 - k} - 1$$

Intervention point

Background :-

At $-3.5 \text{ IP}, 10^{-4} \text{ } D^0$ candidates

fraction collide

At -1.5 IP , $10^{-1.5}$ D° fraction
collide

At OIP, $10^{-2.5}$ D⁰ fraction
collide

As IP $\uparrow$ $\longrightarrow$ quantity $\downarrow$

$$IP \propto \frac{1}{\text{quantity}}$$

$$IP \times \text{quantity} = \text{constant}$$

Second part of range,
IP

$$\frac{IP}{\text{Quantity}} = \text{constant}$$

$$\text{Q } IP = K = \frac{IP}{Q}$$

$$\frac{I_p}{k} = Q$$

and $Q = \frac{k}{I_p}$

$$i \cdot Q = \frac{I_p}{k} = \frac{k}{I_p}$$

$$\frac{I_p}{k} = \frac{k}{I_p}$$

$$I_p^2 = k^2$$

$$F r^2 = k^2$$

$$F p^2 - k^2 = 0$$

$$\therefore Q = F p^2 - k^2$$

Signal

At $-3.5 I_P$, $10^{-4} D^0$ fluctuation coincide

At $-1.5 I_P$, $10^{-1} D^0$ fluctuation coincide

At $0 I_P$, $10^{-3} D^0$ fluctuation coincide

in mean points

As $I_P \uparrow \longrightarrow$ quantity $\uparrow$

$I_P \propto$ quantity

I_P

————— = constant
Quantity

$$\frac{IP}{Q} = k \quad \therefore Q = \frac{IP}{k}$$

from m.c.n to end point,

As $IP \uparrow \longrightarrow \text{Quantity} \downarrow$

$$IP \propto \frac{1}{\text{Quantity}}$$

$IP * \text{Quantity} = \text{constant}$

$$IP * Q = k$$

$$Q = \frac{k}{\quad}$$

I_r

$$\therefore Q = \frac{I_r}{k} = \frac{k}{I_r}$$

$$Q \approx \frac{k^2}{I_p^2} = \left[\frac{k}{I_p} \right]^2$$

total quantity

$$\approx \frac{k^2}{I_p^2} + I_p^2 - k^2$$

$$\approx \frac{k^2 + I_p^4 - k^2 I_p^2}{I_p^2}$$

Thus

$$\frac{4mT}{2k^2 - k}$$

$$- 1 = \frac{k^2 + IP^4 - k^2 IP^2}{IP^2}$$
$$= 0$$

Thus,

equation for quantity of

D^o candidates is mentioned

below:-

$$Q = \frac{4mT}{2k^2 - k} - 1$$

$$= \frac{k^2 + I_p^4 - k^2 I_p^2}{I_p^2}$$

Energy of human beings

Humans are macroscopic objects when compared to dark matter particles. Hence the energy possessed by a human would be the potential energy – which is the energy within the body. This would not take into account the motion of the body externally i.e along a road or any track. This leads to the elimination of the causes and effects of kinetic energy.

$$Q = \frac{4mT}{2k^2 - k} - 1 \approx \frac{4mT}{2k^2 - k}$$

But $E = mc^2$ $\rightarrow$ T

$$Q = \frac{4mT}{2k^2 - k}$$

$$\therefore m = \frac{Q(2k^2 - k)}{4T} \quad \rightarrow \quad \underline{\underline{T}}$$

from I and II,

$$M = \frac{F}{c^2} = \frac{Q[2k^2 - kc]}{4T}$$

$$E = \frac{c^2 Q (2k^2 - k)}{4T}$$

$$\text{Energy} = \frac{Q c^2 (2k^2 - k)}{4T}$$

Energy of human being
= human's potential
energy

$$= m g L$$

$$= M Q g L$$

Maximum height of

lunar being = 7m

$$\therefore E = m * g * h$$

$$\therefore E = 68.6 m g$$

$E_1 =$ Energy of dark matter

$$= \frac{Q c^2 [2k^2 - k]}{4\pi}$$

$F_2 =$ Energy of human beings

$= 68.6 \text{ Mj}$

$$\frac{E_1}{E_2} = \frac{m \times c^2}{6.6 \times 10^{-34}}$$

$$= \frac{(3 \times 10^8)^2}{6.6 \times 10^{-34}}$$

$$= \frac{9 \times 10^{16}}{6.6 \times 10^{-34}}$$

$$= 0.1362 \times 10^{16}$$

$$\approx \frac{0.1312 \times 10^{16}}{Q}$$

$$\approx \frac{131200 \times 10^{10}}{Q} \approx 10^{10}$$

$$\therefore E_1 \approx 10^{10} \text{ TF}_2$$

∴ Energy of dark matter

$\approx 10^{10}$ * Energy of
human being

Hence from the above mentioned mathematical computation, it is derived that Energy of Dark matter and Dark Energy is approximately $[10^{10}]$ times the Energy of the Human being individual.

Since the enormous dark energy impinges and surrounds the human being, this dark energy is also transferred as waves colliding the human body. This leads to imbalances in the human being due to the imbalances in the two energy comparisons.

Higher energy collisions on the lower energy substances lead to weakening of the lower energy bodies.

Figure 1: Dark matter and dark energy

Figure 2: LHC in CERN

Figure 3: CERN

